

METHODS OF TEACHING GYMNASTICS TO PRIMARY SCHOOL PUPILS ON THE BASIS OF NON-TRADITIONAL EXERCISES

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Aim: Development of motor activity, physical fitness of children by means of rhythmic exercises based on initial gymnastics.

Methods: 1. Pedagogical test 2. Pedagogical experience; 3. Heart rate monitoring; 4. Self-examination; 5. Method of mathematical statistics.

Results: As a result of the study, it was found that in children 7-8 years old, on the basis of rhythmic exercises based on initial gymnastics, motor activity increases by 11.4%, and physical fitness-by 11.32%. After the experiment, changes in the statistical reliability of the test results were revealed ($p < 0.05$ and higher, 847 ± 0.9 , $t_{ct} = 1.55$)

Conclusion: The experimental program in comparison with the traditional program of physical education provided for the motor intensity of classes of 75-87% and the intensity of the load, the heart rate in the main part from 87 to 187% per minute, when choosing the means and methods of physical education, the age characteristics of children 7-8years were taken into account. The results of the experiment showed a high efficiency of the program developed during the study and applied in the experimental group in comparison with the traditional program used in the control group.

Keywords: 7-8years old, primary gymnastics, rhythmic exercises, pedagogical experience, motor activity, physical fitness, physical qualities.

I. Introduction.

Priority directions of activity of educational organizations in the field of development of children's sports and selection (selection) of talented youth are defined, one of the main tasks of which was the formation of students' interest in physical culture and sports for physical development and health promotion through conducting classes in primary gymnastics in school educational organizations(1).

In the education system of developed countries, school age plays an important role in the physical and all-round harmonious development of school children. It is during this age period that the foundation of health, proper physical development is laid, physical abilities are formed, and interest in physical culture and sports is formed(2,5).

It is necessary to ensure the possibility of physical development of children and their active movement, to scientifically approach the development of the content and methods of the process of physical development, to solve important issues of physical hardening, increasing endurance, forming an interest in sports activities from childhood, independent thinking in classes and in play activities, to take the first steps in physical culture and sports activities(6,4,8)

The purpose of the study: to improve the motor activity of children in the process of physical education of school educational organizations, which consists in the development of a methodological program and a module of rhythmic exercises.

Objectives of the study: to identify in the course of the study the mechanisms of development of motor activity of children aged 7-8years in school educational organizations. Development of a program of rhythmic exercises aimed at preventing problems of the musculoskeletal system, taking into account the age characteristics of children aged 7-8years. Give practical recommendations based on an improved model of the development of indicators of physical fitness of children in school educational organizations.

II. Methods.

Pedagogical testing. To study and assess the level of physical fitness of respondents aged 7-8 years, tests were conducted on the long jump from a standing position, running in a squat, bending the trunk, leaning forward, running for 10 meters in order to determine the effectiveness of the developed program.

Pedagogical experience. In order to develop physical fitness and determine the motor activity of children aged 7-8 years, experiments were conducted in state schools 76, 38 in Samarkand. The program of the experiment covered the means and methods aimed at solving the problems of physical education of school children. To increase the physical, functional and adaptive capabilities of the body, a group (frontal) method of performing exercises of various types of running and jumping, dancing, outdoor games, and preliminary gymnastic complexes was introduced. From 50 to 70 percent of the content the lesson is devoted to the development of motor activity (see figure 1).

Figure 1. Model of the experimental program.

The experiment was conducted on the basis of a set of exercises, including health, educational, and educational orientation when choosing a program model and tools (see figure 1).

The method of mathematical statistics was used to determine the objectivity and reliability and regularities of data processing obtained during the experiment, and to determine their properties and values. Using the Stuart Fisher criterion, the data was processed in the laptop's Exel program. After the experiment, changes in the statistical reliability of the test results were detected ($p < 0.05$ and higher, 847 ± 0.9 , $t_{ct} = 1.55$).

III. Results and discussion.

In the course of the study, a comparative pedagogical experiment was conducted in order to identify and test the effectiveness of the experimental and testing methodology.

The experiment involved respondents aged 7-8 years from 120 school educational organizations (60 experimental control groups, 60 control groups). At the beginning of the experiment, a comparative analysis of the physical development and physical fitness of the respondents of the experimental-test and control groups was carried out.

In the experimental and control groups of respondents, 30-minute classes were conducted according to a program consisting of a set of rhythmic exercises based on initial gymnastics, three times a week for six months. Those who were in the control group, all this time were engaged in

a permanent traditional program of physical education (the duration and time of classes are similar).

examination of children in the experimental-test and control groups after the experiment showed that the number of children with a predisposition to diseases of the musculoskeletal system in the control group decreased from 17.5% to 14.5%, and in the experimental-test group-from 16.5% to 10.5% (see picture 1).

At the beginning of the experiment, there was no significant difference in the indicators of physical development and the results of physical fitness of the respondents of the experimental-test and control groups.

Picture 2. Relative dynamics of growth of indicators of physical fitness of the experimental-test and control groups during the experiment (% , n = 60).

At the end of the experiment, a one-sided significant change in physical development indicators was observed in both groups. Thus, the increased loads did not have a negative impact on the body of the respondents (as evidenced by the results of pedagogical observations and heart rate monitoring data).

A comparative analysis of the indicators characterizing the physical condition of children in the experimental group at the beginning and at the end of the experiment allowed us to ensure a significant change in the results in all control exercises.

In comparison with the traditional program, the use of the experimental program and the model gave effective advantages, which positively affected the dynamics of physical fitness and motor activity indicators (see picture 2).

Picture 3. Dynamics of heart rate in physical education classes of experimental-test and control groups.

Heart rate monitoring data showed that the loads in all parts of the experiment corresponded to the age of the respondents, the recommendations of the "First step" program and state requirements. The analysis of the pulse dynamics in the classes of the experimental-test and control groups showed that physical exercises in the experimental-test group, in comparison with the classes in the control group, have a more positive effect on the child's body (see picture 3). Thus, the pulse measurement data confirm the effectiveness of the experimental-test method:

- when choosing the means and methods of physical education, the age characteristics of children aged 7-8 years were taken into account.

IV. Conclusion.

The results of the respondents of the experimental group were good compared to the results of the respondents of the control group, which led to a positive change in statistical reliability. After the experiment, changes in the statistical reliability of the test results were revealed ($p < 0.05$ and higher, 847 ± 0.9 , $t_{st} = 1.55$). Shuttle running - from 11.22 s to 10.61 s, long jumps from a standing position - from 103.27 cm to 110.61 cm, torso flexion - from 13.11 to 26.05, crawling for 10 meters - from 7.65 to 7.01 s, leaning forward - from 2.65 cm to 4.61 cm. The growth dynamics can be traced, and the listed factors confirming the effectiveness of the program indicate that we have achieved our goal. According to the results of the experiment, it was found that in children 7-8 years old who studied according to the traditional program in CG, the length and weight of the body increased by 3.7 and 2.8%, respectively, by the end of the experimental period, and in EG who studied according to the improved experimental program, these indicators were 5.6 and 4.7%.

In other words, there were no statistically significant changes in the functional parameters observed by anthropometric and physical indicators in children brought up in EG, in CG. Physical abilities (shuttle running, long jumps from a standing position, torso flexion, leaning forward, crawling up to 10 m) also differed in that children with EG had more intensive growth than those with CG, the relative dynamics of growth in physical fitness indicators is reflected in Table 1 and Picture 3.

The result of the study proves the effectiveness of experimentally tested methods for the development of physical fitness of children for motor activity.

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